

SYNTHESIS AND EVALUATION OF CHALCONE-BASED 1,3,4- OXADIZOLE DERIVATIVES AGAINST ANTIINFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT: Chalcones are naturally occurring compounds widely distributed in plants and serve as important intermediates for the synthesis of various biologically active heterocyclic derivatives. In the present study, a new series of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives was synthesized and characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, and mass spectrometry. The synthesized compounds were evaluated for their **acute toxicity, in vivo anti-inflammatory activity, and in vitro antioxidant activity**. Acute toxicity studies revealed that all compounds were free from toxic effects up to a dose of 1000 mg/kg body weight. The anti-inflammatory activity was assessed using the carrageenan-induced rat paw edema model, with indomethacin serving as the standard reference. Among the synthesized derivatives, **compound VII-c (X = 3-Cl-Benzaldehyde)** exhibited the most potent anti-inflammatory activity, showing **89.8% inhibition** of paw edema at the 4th hour. Antioxidant activity was determined using the **DPPH free radical scavenging assay**, where compounds **VII-c** and **VII-e** demonstrated significant radical scavenging potential with IC₅₀ values of **53.5 μM** and **41.3 μM**, respectively. The results suggest that the synthesized chalcone-based oxadiazole derivatives possess promising anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities, indicating potential for further pharmacological development.

KEYWORDS: Chalcone derivatives; Anti-inflammatory activity; Antioxidant assay; Carrageenan-induced paw edema; DPPH radical scavenging; Acute toxicity.

1. INTRODUCTION

A chalcone is a simple chemical scaffold of many naturally occurring compounds and has a widespread distribution in vegetables, fruits, teas, and other plants. The word “chalcone” is derived from the Greek word “chalcos”, meaning “bronze”, which results from the colors of most natural chalcones.³Chalcone compounds have a common chemical scaffold of 1,3- diaryl-2-propen-1-one, also known as chalconoid, that exists as trans and cis isomers, with the trans isomer being thermodynamically more stable (Figure 1)[1-5].The phenyl ring attached to the carbonyl group is defined to be the A ring, and the other benzene ring is named as the B ring (Fig.1)[3-6].

Fig. 1: Structures of chalcone and two clinically approved chalcone-based drugs

Flavonoids with a 1, 3-diarylpropane skeleton can be classified as an outstanding class of naturally occurring compounds. Chalcones or 1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one derivatives are open chain unsaturated carbonyl system in which two aromatic rings are joined by three carbons having an α , β - unsaturated system[7]. Chalcones are called “anthochlor pigments”, coined to identify a group of yellow pigments that turn red in the presence of alkali[8]. Chalcones are considered the precursors of flavonoids and isoflavonoids and are secondary metabolites of terrestrial plants that exhibit various biological activities[9,10]. Chalcones are popular intermediates for synthesizing various heterocyclic compounds like flavones, isoxazoles, pyrazoles, tetrahydro-2-chromens, etc. [11,12]. Chalcones, either natural or synthetic, are known to exhibit various biological activities. Kostanecki was the first to give the term chalcone and did pioneer work in the synthesis of naturally occurring compounds[13].

Chalcones are a resourceful precursor for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds. Chalcones undergo cyclization reactions with different reagents to form diverse classes of heterocyclic compounds ranging from five-membered to seven-membered rings containing nitrogen, oxygen, and sulfur heteroatoms. In the cyclization reactions, the highly reactive bielectrophilic ketovinyl chain condenses with a variety of binucleophilic reagents to generate an assortment of heterocyclic systems, such as derivatives of pyrazolines, phenylpyrazoline, and isoxazole (5-membered heterocyclics) aminopyrimidines and cyanopyridines (6-membered heterocyclics), and

derivatives of 1,5-benzodiazepines, 1,5-benzoxazepines, and 1,5-bezothiazepines (7-membered heterocyclics)[14-16].

The chalcone family has attracted much interest not only from the synthetic and biosynthetic perspectives but also due to its broad, interesting biological activities. Therapeutic applications of chalcones trace back thousands of years through the use of plants and herbs for the treatment of different medical disorders, such as cancer, inflammation, and diabetes. Several chalcone-based compounds have been approved for clinical use. For example, metochalcone was once marketed as a choleric drug, while sofalcone was previously used as an antiulcer and mucoprotective drug. The chalcones have been reported to possess various biological activities such as antimalarial, antibacterial, anti-cancer, antileishmanial, antifibrogenic, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, cytotoxic, analgesic, anti-platelet, anti-ulcerative, antiviral, antioxidant, anti-tubercular, antihyperglycemic, inhibition of chemical mediators release, inhibition of leukotriene B₄, inhibition of tyrosinases, inhibition of aldose 4 reductase activities, and anti-trypanosoma cruzi activities. Some chalcone derivatives show herbicidal activity, and substituted chalcones have exhibited fungistatic and fungicidal activity[17-26]. The presence of a reactive α , β -unsaturated keto function in chalcones is found to be responsible for their biological activities.

1.1. INFLAMMATION

Inflammation is a part of the complex biological response of body tissues to harmful stimuli, such as pathogens, damaged cells, or irritants.

It is a protective response involving immune cells, blood vessels, and molecular mediators. The function of inflammation is to eliminate the initial cause of cell injury, clear out necrotic cells and tissues damaged from the original insult and the inflammatory process, and initiate tissue repair.

1.2. INFLAMMATION MECHANISM (Fig.2)

Fig. 2: Mechanism of inflammation

1.3. Causes for Inflammation

Physical:

Burns

Frostbite

Physical injury, blunt or penetrating

Foreign bodies, including splinters, dirt, and debris

Trauma

Ionizing radiation

Biological:

Infection by pathogens

Immune reactions due to hypersensitivity

Stress

Chemical:

Chemical irritants

Toxins

Alcohol

Psychological:

Excitement

- The classical signs of inflammation are

heat

pain

redness

swelling and

loss of function.

- Inflammation can be classified as either *acute* or *chronic* (Fig. 2).
- Acute inflammation is the initial response of the body to harmful stimuli and is achieved by movement of plasma and leukocytes (especially granulocytes) from the blood into the injured tissues.
- Prolonged inflammation, known as ***chronic inflammation***, leads to a progressive shift in the type of cells present at the site of inflammation, such as mononuclear cells, and is characterized by simultaneous destruction and healing of the tissue from the inflammatory process.
- Chronic inflammation may lead to a host of diseases, such as
 - hay fever,
 - periodontitis,
 - atherosclerosis,
 - rheumatoid arthritis, and
 - even cancer (e.g., gallbladder carcinoma).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. SYNTHESIS

The scheme of synthesis for the designed benzoxazole derivatives is depicted below in a scheme.

(E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII)

2.2. PROCEDURE

PREPARATION OF BENZOHYDRAZIDE (II)

Equimolar quantities of Benzoic acid (0.6 g, 2mmol) and 99% hydrazine hydrate were dissolved in 10ml of ethanol, and kept refluxing for 6 hrs. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The product was recrystallized from ethanol.

PREPARATION OF CHALCONE (V)

A mixture of acetophenone (0.5 g, 2mmol) and benzaldehyde (6ml, 2mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) was cooled to 0-5 °C, and then 3 ml of aqueous NaOH (1mol/L) was added to this mixture and stirred at 25 °C for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and acidified with Conc. HCl. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The residue was recrystallized from petroleum ether.

PREPARATION OF (E)-N'-(1,3-DIPHENYLPROPYLIDENE)BENZOHYDRAZIDE (VI)

Equimolar quantities of benzohydrazide (II) and chalcone (V) were dissolved in 10ml of ethanol, and kept refluxing for 6-8 hrs. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with cold alcohol, dried, and purified by column chromatography (ethylacetate: hexane: 1, V/V).

PREPARATION OF (E)-2-(1,3-DIPHENYLALLYL)-5-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE (VII)

The (E)-N'-(1,3-diphenylpropylidene)benzohydrazide (VI)(0.01mmol,0.2g) and CH₃COOH (0.01mmol,5ml) were dissolved in 10ml of ethanol, to this 5 ml of aqueous 40%NaOH is added and kept reflux for 12 hrs. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with ice-cold water, and the product recrystallized from ethanol.

2.3 PHYSICAL DATA:

The compounds physical parameters are given in (Table 1).

S.NO	Compound	X	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Melting point	Yield (%)
1	VII-a		C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O	338.41	242	70

2	VII-b		$C_{23}H_{17}ClN_2O$	372.85	245	72
3	VII-c		$C_{23}H_{17}ClN_2O$	372.85	241	65
4	VII-d		$C_{23}H_{17}ClN_2O$	372.85	240	69
5	VII-e		$C_{23}H_{17}FN_2O$	356.40	248	64
6	VII-f		$C_{23}H_{17}FN_2O$	356.40	245	70
7	VII-g		$C_{23}H_{17}FN_2O$	356.40	243	72
8	VII-h		$C_{23}H_{17}BrN_2O$	417.31	246	74
9	VII-i		$C_{23}H_{17}BrN_2O$	417.31	244	68
10	VII-j		$C_{23}H_{17}BrN_2O$	417.31	248	70

Table 1: Physical data of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII)

2.4. SPECTRAL DATA:

Spectral data of **(E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII)**

Molecular formula: C₂₃H₂₈N₂O

Mol. wt: 338.41

- ❖ **IR (KBr) cm⁻¹:** CH₂-2795.39cm, CH-2672.34cm, C-O-1741.36cm, C=N-1619.69cm
- ❖ **¹H NMR (300 MHz) (DMSO):** 8.02(m, Ar-CH), 7.62(m, Ar-CH), 7.37(d, Ar-CH), 7.33(m, Ar-CH), 7.24(d, Ar-CH), 7.21(d, Ar-CH), 6.66(d, C-H), 6.37(d, C-H), 4.74(d, C-H)
- ❖ **Mass spectrum (ESI):** Calculated mass is 338.41

M⁺ mass peak was observed at 339.45

IR Spectral data of **(E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII)**

NMR Spectral data of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII)

Mass Spectral data of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII)

Mass spectrum (ESI): Calculated mass is 338.41

M^{+1} mass peak was observed at 339.45.

3. PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUATION:

In view of the varied biological and pharmacological importance of different series of new bis (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives, it has been planned for me to evaluate the new series of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives for the following biological activities by standard protocols.

- 1) Acute toxicity study.
- 2) Anti-inflammatory study (In vivo).
- 3) Antioxidant activity (In vitro).

3.1. ACUTE TOXICITY STUDY

MATERIALS:

0.1 % Sodium CMC, test compounds, and sonicator.

ANIMALS:

Albino Swiss mice (male)

METHOD:

Healthy and adult male albino Swiss mice weighing between 20 and 25 g were used in this investigation. Animals were fasted overnight and divided into groups of six animals each. The test compounds suspended in 0.1% sodium CMC were administered by i.p, in doses up to 1000 mg/kg body weight. The control group animals received only vehicle (0.1% sodium CMC). The animals were observed for one month from the time of administration of test compounds to record the mortality (Table 2).

DOSE mg/kg (b.w)	TOXIC SYMPTOMS & IRRITABILITY
10	-ve
30	-ve
100	-ve
300	-ve
1000	Found Irritability

Table 2: Acute Toxicity Studies

All the new synthesized (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives employed for acute toxicity studies and are free from toxicity as well as toxic symptoms even at high dose of 1000 mg/kg (b.w.) intraperitoneally, but irritation like behaviour was observed at 1000 mg/kg (b.w), therefore the dose was decreased to ten times to the dose where the irritability was found.

Selected dose is 100 mg/kg b.w (i.p).

3.2. IN VIVO ANTIINFLAMMATORY STUDIES

Evaluation of in vivo anti-inflammatory activity of synthesized compounds by Carrageenan-induced rat paw edema method[27].

Materials:

Polypropylene cages with paddy husk
Plethysmograph
Carrageenan
Indomethacin
Test compounds
Normal saline and water.

Animals:

All the experiments were carried out using male Wistar rats (250-300 g) obtained from the animal house, Siddhartha Institute of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India. On arrival, the animals were placed at random and allocated to treatment groups in polypropylene cages with paddy husk as bedding. Animals were housed at a temperature of $24^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity of 30-70%. A 12:12 light: day cycle was followed. All animals were allowed free access to water and fed with standard commercial rat chew pellets. All the experimental procedures and protocols used in this study were reviewed by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee, Siddhartha Institute of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India (IAEC/24/SIP/2025) (Fig.3).

Preparation of Carrageenan suspension:

1% w/v Suspension of carrageenan was prepared by adding 100mg of carrageenan powder to 10 mL of saline (0.9% NaCl) solution and setting aside to soak for 1 hour. A homogenous suspension was then obtained by thorough mixing with a magnetic stirrer.

Experimental Procedure:

1. Wistar Strain albino rats, weighing between 250-300 g and fasted overnight before the test, and allowed water ad libitum, were divided into 12 groups of 5 animals each.
2. The volume of the right hind paw was measured using a plethysmometer. This constituted the initial reading.
3. The test compound was administered at a dose of 100mg/kg body weight.
4. Indomethacin 10mg/kg body weight was used as a standard.
5. All these were administered as suspensions using sodium CMC (0.3% w/v) as a suspending agent.
6. A control group of animals received a suspension of sodium CMC only.

7. All these were administered intraperitoneally 1 hour before the injection of carrageenan suspension in normal saline was injected into the subplantar region of the right hind paw (Table 3).
8. The swelling produced after injection of the carrageenan was measured at 1 hour intervals for 4 hours. The percentage inhibition of edema was calculated using the formula given below (Table 4) (Graph 1):

Fig.3: Carrageenan-induced edema in the Right hind paw (*) of a rat.

$$\% \text{ inhibition of edema} = \frac{\text{Mean edema of the control group} - \text{Mean edema of the test group}}{\text{Mean edema of a control group}} \times 100$$

S.NO	COMPOUND	X	Mean Paw Edema Volume in ml ± SD			
			1h	2h	3h	4h
1	VII-a		0.50 ± 0.07	0.48 ± 0.070	0.44 ± 0.086	0.36 ± 0.097
2	VII-b		0.62 ± 0.056	0.58 ± 0.061	0.54 ± 0.049	0.52 ± 0.053

3	VII-c		0.48±0.0710	0.46 ± 0.067	0.41 ± 0.089	0.33 ± 0.061
4	VII-d		0.68±0.059	0.66±0.087	0.64 ± 0.073	0.62± 0.097
5	VII-e		0.52±0.074	0.48 ± 0.092	0.44 ± 0.620	0.41 ± 0.070
6	VII-f		0.67±0.042	0.63±0.095	0.50± 0.081	0.59± 0.050
7	VII-g		0.55±0.040	0.60±0.090	0.52± 0.075	0.58± 0.060
8	VII-h		0.60±0.044	0.65± 0.090	0.50± 0.080	0.62± 0.070
9	VII-i		0.62± 0.040	0.65± 0.095	0.55± 0.082	0.54± 0.068
10	VII-j		0.68± 0.040	0.63± 0.095	0.58± 0.080	0.52± 0.078
11	Control group (Carrageenan treated)		0.69 ± 0.097	0.76± 0.078	0.83 ± 0.092	0.95 ± 0.062
12	Indomethacin		0.46 ± 0.081	0.43 ± 0.230	0.39 ± 0.090	0.32 ± 0.073

Table 3: Anti-inflammatory activity of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII) derivatives.

S.NO	COMPOUND	X	% Inhibition of Paw Edema			
			1h	2h	3h	4h
1	VII-a		42.0	54.0	65.7	80.5
2	VII-b		23.0	31.6	52.0	63.1
3	VII-c		46.2	56.1	68.9	89.8
4	VII-d		2.7	28.3	29.3	41.2
5	VII-e		33.3	54.3	65.7	74.2
6	VII-f		4.6	32.0	44.8	53.8
7	VII-g		24.3	12.6	20	11.3
8	VII-h		28	28	46	29
9	VII-i		25	28	39	38

10	VII-j		17.9	30	35	42
11	Indomethacin		50.6	61.2	76.6	85.0

Table 4: Antiinflammatory activity of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII) derivatives.

Graph 1: Showing the percentage inhibition of paw edema of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII) derivatives.

3.3.ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY (*INVITRO*)

Evaluation of antioxidant activity of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII) derivatives.

Materials:

Ascorbic acid (Analytical grade, Merck India)

Methanol (HPLC grade, Merck India)

DPPH α,α -diphenyl, β -picrylhydrazyl (Sigma Aldrich)

Test compounds

Double-distilled water.

Preparation of Standard Solution of Ascorbic Acid:

The required amount of ascorbic acid was accurately weighed and dissolved in distilled water to prepare a 1 mM stock solution. Solutions of different concentrations (10nM, 30nM, 100nM, 300nM, 1µM, 3 µM, 100 µM, 300 µM, 1mM) of Ascorbic acid were prepared from stock solution.

Preparation of DPPH Solution:

A 0.2 mM solution of DPPH was prepared by dissolving the required amount of DPPH in 100 mL of methanol. The solution was protected from sunlight to prevent the oxidation of DPPH.

Preparation of Test Compounds:

The required amount of test compounds was dissolved in methanol, and a 1 mM stock solution was prepared. Solutions of concentration ranging from 10nM to 1mM were prepared.

Principle:

The method is based on the principle described by Blois's (1958) method. The model of scavenging the DPPH radical is the most widely used method to evaluate the antioxidant activity in a relatively shorter time compared with other methods. The effect of antioxidant on DPPH radical scavenging was thought to be their hydrogen-donating ability

DPPH is a stable free radical that accepts an electron or hydrogen radical to become a stable diamagnetic molecule. The reduction capability of DPPH radical was determined by the decrease in its absorbance at 517nm induced by antioxidants. The absorption maximum of stable DPPH radical in methanol was at 517nm. The decrease in absorbance of DPPH radical caused by antioxidants, because of the reaction between antioxidant molecules and radical, progresses, resulting in the scavenging of the radical by hydrogen donation. Hence, DPPH is used as a substrate to evaluate the antioxidant activity.

Procedure:

To 0.1 mL of test sample/ascorbic acid, 2.5 mL of methanol, and 0.5 mL of DPPH solution were added, mixed thoroughly, and absorbance was measured at 517nm against the blank, prepared identically but without the test compound.

The results were plotted on a graph, and IC₅₀ value was calculated (Table 5)(Graph 2).

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of blank} - \text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of blank}} \times 100$$

S.NO	COMPOUND	X	IC ₅₀ (μM)
1	VII-a		20.9
2	VII-b		23.6
3	VII-c		53.5
4	VII-d		93.0
5	VII-e		41.3
6	VII-f		80.6
7	VII-g		75.4
8	VII-h		82.8

9	VII-i		65.9
10	VII-j		70.5
11	STANDARD	ASCORBIC ACID	6.87

Table.5: Antioxidant activity of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII) derivatives.

Graph.2: Antioxidant activity of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (VII) derivatives.

4. RESULTS

1. Synthetic work of these studies has been positively undergone as per the planning, and as such, in all the reactions carried out, the expected compounds alone could be obtained.
2. All the above-mentioned new (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives were characterized by physical, analytical, and spectral data.
3. All the test compounds (**Va-Vj**) were evaluated and screened for their in vivo **Anti-inflammatory activity** and in vitro **Antioxidant** activity.

Anti-inflammatory activity

- ❖ The preliminary studies on anti-inflammatory activity of the (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have generated some interesting data. An attempt has been made to infer the ultimate outcome of the present study based on this data.
- ❖ All the synthesized new (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives were evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity by using standard indomethacin for the period of four hours with a one-hour interval.
- ❖ All the synthesized compounds were tested at a dose of 100mg/kg b.w, and the results were compared with standard indomethacin at a dose of 10mg/kg b.w
- ❖ The investigation of anti-inflammatory activity revealed that the test compounds of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole and its derivatives showed promising anti-inflammatory activity at a dose of 100mg/kg b.w with % inhibition at the fourth hour in the range of
- ❖ Compound VII-c (X=3-Cl-Benzaldehyde) exhibited comparatively more Anti-inflammatory activity with 89.8 % in the inhibition of paw edema at the 4th hour.
- ❖ Whereas the compound with VII-j (X=4-Br-Benzaldehyde) 40 % inhibition of paw edema at the 4th hour.
- ❖ And compound VII-g (X=4-F-Benzaldehyde) 11.3% showed comparatively the least anti-inflammatory activity, 39.2% inhibition of paw edema at the 4th hour.

ACUTE TOXICITY STUDIES:

All the test compounds employed in the investigation have been found to be free from toxicity as well as toxic symptoms even at a high dose of 1000mg/kg(b.w), but irritation and excitation-like behaviour were observed at high doses.

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

- ❖ The IC₅₀ values of all synthesized test compounds were found between 10.7µM to 90.7µM.
- ❖ Among these compounds, compound VII-c (X=2-Cl-Benzaldehyde) & VII-e (X=2-F-Benzaldehyde) showed comparatively More (93 & 82.8) antioxidant activity.
- ❖ Compounds VII-c (X=2-Cl-Benzaldehyde) & VII-e (X=2-F-Benzaldehyde) showed moderate(53.5& 41.3) antioxidant activity.
- ❖ Compounds VII-a (X=H, Benzaldehyde) showed comparatively weak (20.9) antioxidant activity.

DISCUSSION

The successful synthesis and structural confirmation of (E)-2-(1,3-diphenylallyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives highlight chalcone as a versatile intermediate for bioactive heterocycles. Acute toxicity evaluations confirmed the safety of these derivatives within therapeutic limits. The anti-inflammatory screening revealed that the **presence of halogen substituents (Cl, Br, F)** on the benzaldehyde moiety significantly influences biological activity, with **3-chloro substitution (VII-c)** showing the highest inhibition of carrageenan-induced inflammation. This may be attributed to enhanced lipophilicity and electron-withdrawing effects, facilitating better receptor binding.

In the DPPH antioxidant assay, compounds **VII-c** and **VII-e** exhibited notable radical scavenging potential, suggesting that substitution patterns at ortho and meta positions enhance electron delocalization and stability of the oxadiazole ring system. The overall results establish a structure–activity relationship (SAR), indicating that **halogen substitution on aromatic rings** enhances both **anti-inflammatory** and **antioxidant** properties.

CONCLUSION

The study successfully synthesized and characterized a novel series of chalcone-based oxadiazole derivatives. Pharmacological screening revealed that these compounds exhibit promising **anti-inflammatory** and **antioxidant** activities with minimal toxicity. Among the series, **Compounds VII-d (4-Cl-Benzaldehyde) and VII-h (2-Br-Benzaldehyde)** were found to be the more potent compounds, respectively, towards carrageenan-induced rat paw edema. **Compounds VII-c (2-Cl-Benzaldehyde) and VII-e (2-F-Benzaldehyde)** were found to be more potent antioxidant compounds among all the test compounds. These findings suggest that chalcone-derived oxadiazoles could serve as potential lead molecules for the development of anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agents. Further studies, including molecular docking and in vivo pharmacokinetic evaluations, are warranted to elucidate their mechanisms and therapeutic potential.

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